

Value Crisis & its Remediation through Education

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Abstract

Education is a process of initiating the learner to good life. But present day, the prime focus of education is to transmission of knowledge and cultivation of occupational skills for getting a job. But in this process of balancing our pace with modernization, westernization and Materialism, we ourselves are eroding the core of human values. The atmosphere of conflict and turmoil, the rate of crime and delinquency, murder, alcoholism, drug addiction, suicide etc has increased. This erosion of human value is not only creeping in western society but it is spreading in India as well which is said to be the land of values. The deepening value crisis in the Indian society is casting its evil shadow in all walks of our life. Even after fifty years of progress in different fields-economic, industrial, scientific, educational-it is doubtful if we are moving towards creation of a just society, a happy society, a good society. The promises of the bryst with the destiny, and the dreams of prosperity, social wellbeing and human happiness are proving to be false. This value crisis is prevailing at individual level as well as it is affecting our society. Value is felling down day by day. We have to think about this value crisis and the ways for getting out of this situation.

Introduction:

Education is necessarily a process of inculcating values to equip the learner lead a life-a kind of life that is satisfying to the individual in accordance with the cherished values and ideals of the society. Philosophers, spiritual leaders and educationists of our country, all in various ways, have emphasized the role of education for character development", "bringing out the latent potentialities and inherent qualities' and developing an 'integrated personality' for the well being of the individual and the society at large. But present day, the prime focus of education is to transmission of knowledge and cultivation of occupational skills for getting a job. Education is becoming day by day more or less materialistic and the values are slowly given up. The modern India is being educated mainly with the bread and butter aim of education and as a result as a most of our graduates run after money, power, comforts without caring for any values. Moral, Religious and spiritual education is being deliberately neglected in our educational system. In the process of balancing our pace with modernization, westernization and Materialism, we ourselves are eroding the core of human values. India is passing through a period of value crisis. Even after fifty years of progress in different fields-economic, industrial, scientific, educational-it is doubtful if we are moving towards creation of a just society, a happy society, a good society. Massive industrial infrastructure is being built with an increasing insistence on efficiency needed for an industrial society, leaving no room for the growth of humane and spiritual consciousness. Our social life is full of corruption. violence. hypocrisy, exploitation, disparity and disruption. The erosion of values is now a national phenomenon. so complex

and gigantic that a more balanced curriculum, new learning materials and competent teachers, alone can correct this phenomenon (NPE. 1986). It is a daunting task to examine the nature of today's value crisis in this gloomy climate. Yet, there is no escape from it either. One must grapple with it as best as one can. Value crisis is spreading its wings in all spheres of our life. These spheres may be categorized as individual and societal.

Value Crisis at Individual Level:

In this era of globalisation and so called progressivism, the sole aim of all the individual has become attainment of personal success. The rat race to this success commands enthusiastic support of the powerful middle and elite classes. Their upbringing and enculturation have tuned them for single minded pursuit of career growth and economic success. All other life values which give meaning, worth and fullness to human existence are seen as roadblocks and unnecessary diversions from the high road to material success.

Similarly, the concept of a good life has become the synonymous for unrestricted enjoyment of sensuous pleasures and fulfilment of unlimited desires. It is defined as a situation of consumerist haven filled with all kinds of artifacts for comfort and luxury. In this time all believe in the slogan of higher the quantity of consumption, better the quality of life'. The new economic policies of liberalisation and globalisation have further propelled this ever aggressive march of consumerism. It does not mean that the commonly accepted notion of success and good life i.e., natural human inclinations for economic betterment, material comforts and enjoyment of life's pleasures is totally wrongful. They certainly are important components of a good life. But they are not the most

important and single component of a good life. They are not the ultimate goals of human striving for happiness and fulfilment. The modern value crisis is mainly due to the excessive overplaying of the importance of material values of life, and consequent down playing of other life values like the moral, aesthetic and spiritual.

A related dimension of the value crisis is the increasing respectability of selfish individualism. It takes the form of exclusive concern for personal gains without any consideration for the common good. In every situation the guiding principle and the main question is, "what is in it for me?" Such selfish persons use their friends, parents, relatives, and all other human relationships merely as means for personal advancement, without cherishing them or giving them much in return. They develop their talents, skills and knowledge, not because they make for a good person or a good society, but only to encase them at the opportune moment for gaining personal advantage. Such self-seeking, careerist ambitions are encouraged, even admired, by the modern professional and managerial class as the desirable virtues of motivation, goal-orientation, competitive spirit, etc.

Another dimension of the value crisis at the individual level is the steep rise in the rights-consciousness, along with a steeper decline in the duty-consciousness. No one is talking about the duties and responsibilities of individuals and groups, towards each other and towards the collective whole. The common ethical principle that the rights of one can be fulfilled only if others performed their duties seems to have been forgotten.

The third dimension of this crisis is the common mentality of adopting double standards of value judgment, a much higher one for others and a much lower one for us. Even the smallest mistakes of others do not escape our censorious scrutiny while we casually ignore or explain away our own wrongful conducts and malicious intentions. We refuse to accept any part of responsibility for the evils around us, let alone take initiative to do something about them. This duality of value standards also exhibits itself in the wide gap between profession and practice. The very persons, who talk about high ideals, give frequent quotations in Sanskrit, exhort us to follow examples of national heroes, stoop down to lowest levels of conduct for their own personal gains. And they have little qualm about it because it is generally accepted that words need not match deeds. This has generated a pervasive disvalue of mistrust in social intercourse where it is difficult to accept any statement on its face value.

Value Crisis at Societal Level:

We live in society. An individual's success has no meaning until it is approved by society.

Anybody who tries to achieve success works this for getting a better position in his society. The Indian society has traditionally been a group-oriented society. Although this group consciousness has generally been limited to caste, clan and village community, it did provide a counterbalancing communitarian pull to the tendency of selfish individualism. With the ascendancy of ideologies and isms like/ individualism, consumerism, rights-ism, etc., this communitarian feeling has declined, particularly amongst the middle and the elite classes. Nor has it been replaced by a larger social consciousness which prompts the feeling of oneness with the society. It is this social consciousness which reminds us that all our individual attainments are derived from the society and have validity only in relation to it. We are entitled to fulfilment of our rightful expectations only when we perform our social duties and obligations efficiently and enthusiastically. It is this social consciousness which prompts individuals to work for the promotion of common social good, at least not to harm it for the sake of their individual gains. This deadening of social consciousness has reduced our sensitivity to a variety of social evils like, poverty, injustice, exploitation, caste, class and gender inequalities, etc. The better endowed citizens, whose sensitivities and attitudes affect social transformation, have closed their eyes to these problems and have retreated into their own citadels of comfort and prosperity.

The realisation that even for our personal growth we have to fulfil our social obligations is one level of social consciousness. At a deeper level we identify more closely with our society when we say 'it is my society'. This emotional identification serves the psychological need for a larger group identity. It generates a sense of pride in the achievements, the glory, and the common heritage of the society. This belongingness also creates a sense of responsibility for working towards removal of social inequalities, disharmonies and afflictions of various kinds. It nurtures the social virtues of care and concern. Without it society ceases to be a web of social relationships' for the nurturance of human values, human happiness and human growth. It becomes a cold, numerical collectivity of individuals and groups, and worse still, a tension filled, strife torn, ruthless and oppressive system, governed by the jungle law of might is right. Lack of social consciousness and social cohesiveness are the major features of the contemporary value crisis at the societal level.

The two most devalued words in our society today are politics and politician. Political pursuit has become unscrupulous manipulation for grabbing power and using it for selfish, partisan ends. Political parties are organized less on the lines of ideologies and socio-economic programmes, and

more on the basis of caste, religion, and regional identities. Instead of acting as a unite force for reconciling narrow group interests they have become a divisive force. fanning fissiparous tendencies. Corruption, scams, nexus with black marketeers and criminals have become the main features of the political character. The common citizen, who in theory is the sovereign in a democracy, is forced to remain a helpless, mute spectator to the open loot of public funds by politicians and conniving public servants.

In this era of progressivism, the gains of economic progress have been concerned by the small upper class. The gap between the rich and the poor has widened resulting in increased social tensions and strifes. It is going in the path of Markownikoff's rule of rich becomes richer and poor becomes poorer'. The society has become divided into two classes, a small but economically and socially powerful class which is happily busy raising its living standards to the international levels, and the much larger but disempowered class which is condemned to remain deprived of even the minimum needs of a civilized life. In its crassly materialistic perceptions the new economic order has little place for human happiness.

Indian society is known for its strong family bond system which used to be a source of value inculcation. Individual learnt here the values of sharing and caring, of reconciling divergent needs and personalities, of subordinating individual interests to the collective interests of the family, of co-operative living. But with the emergence of new economic world, joint family is disappearing and nuclear family is taking its place where the demands of career success and the necessities of consumerist fulfilment leave little time and energy for value inculcation. Instead of being a social and human unit the family is becoming more of an economic unit where the child is conditioned to work single minded for career success, to meet the competition in all fields and to become worldly wise.

The Way Out:

The way out of this crisis will have to be negotiated between various opposing perceptions, ideas and attitudes about life-values. It will require creative intellectual effort of the highest order. It will also need all the wisdom that we can marshal. Therein lies our greatest weakness. The curse of centuries of political subjugation, economic exploitation and cultural stagnation is not so much in the defilement of the socio-economic order but in crushing out the spirit of rational enquiry from our intellectual temper. The crisis situation demands vigorous exploration and generation of new ideas in all dimensions of life values-social, aesthetic, ethical and spiritual. Collectively they can all be put under the umbrella term 'Human Values'. Its core

philosophical concepts would require creative synthesis of the modern humanist and communitarian thoughts on human life and society, and the holistic Indian world view.

Who will bring about this new value revolution? Our traditional institutional structures for value generation and transmission, the gurukulas and the ancient universities, decayed long ago. It is this noble human spirit of progress, based on continuous refinement of socio-cultural processes and philosophical enquiry into the nature of good life, and the whole spectrum of human values, that needs to be revived today. It would be pathetic to seek solutions for modern problems in ancient prescriptions meant for an all-together different socio-cultural milieu. Therefore, in this time the teacher has the most pivotal role to play in the pursuit and promotion of human values. All over the world, it is accepted that the future will be the product of what is being done in the present day schools. This depends largely on the competence as well as dedication of teachers. Real, good and dedicated teachers, who are able to provide proper guidance to the students, have to be identified, professionally trained, promoted and provided appropriate economic status, which attract the best and most talented persons to the teaching profession. It is very important that during the teacher education programme, the teacher are introduced to the concept of value development and also made aware of the methods and techniques keeping in view the physical and psychological development of the students to promote human values. It is important to develop the vision of the teachers in such a way that they can incorporate suitable strategies and methods while teaching any subject. Thus, we see that it is the true teacher who can change the students and produce right citizens.

It is obvious that teachers are the main source of value inculcation among future citizen for the formation of a value based society. Hence, it is needed to train them properly so that they can become an ideal teacher and produce good citizen. Teacher education is an integral component of the educational system. The functions of teacher education is to produce good teachers, the good teacher is one who develop proper value system among children. Curriculum is the important tools in the hands of the teacher. The pragmatic, skill oriented and responsible teacher education programmes will help to prepare skilled teachers through in-service and pre-service programmes, value based curriculum, residential teacher education programme, co-curricular activities etc. A nation concerned with value crisis needs teacher who are professionally committed and prepared to present a value based model of interaction with their learners. References:

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